

Cyanide : the Unique Ligand

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THERE are a number of properties which as a whole justify the statement: cyanide is not simply one of the many ligands, it is unique. To support this view, we shall consider the following points:

- i) Bonding character of cyanide ion and cyano complexes;
- ii) Formation of cyanide bridged complexes;
- iii) Formation of mixed ligand complexes;
- iv) Stability of the cyano complexes;
- v) Redox behaviour of cyanide;
- vi) Biological and prebiotic importance.

This list is certainly not exhaustive; e.g. cyano-complexes are extremely interesting from point of view of their photochemistry, but this and other properties will not be discussed in this paper.

Bonding properties of cyanide ion: CN^- is isoelectronic with the following diatomic molecules and ions: N_2 , CO , NO^+ and C_2^{2-} the electronic configuration which is

There is one σ and two π bonds between the carbon and nitrogen atom. Evidently there are a number of possibilities for bonding to a metal ion. Cyanide is an ambidentate ligand but it is certain that carbon has a much higher tendency to make a bond to any of the metal ions than the nitrogen atom. There is no definite evidence for the side-on bonding

nevertheless the bonding may have a considerable π character. CN^- is an efficient π -bonding ligand which results in that the electron density of the donor atom decreases and becomes more receptive for back-donation from the d_{π} electrons of the metal ion, if there are such electrons available at all. A good chemical evidence for the π -bonding is the stabilisation of low oxidation states of transition metal ions by cyanide ion. As it is well known zero and univalent nickel cyano-complexes easily can be prepared. As Jones have pointed out¹, the intensity of the infra-red active cyanide stretching vibration (ν_{σ}) is a measure of the extent of metal cyanide π -bonding.

In all cases where structural data are available cyanide is bonded to the metal centre via the carbon

end. This is in sharp contrast with the organic derivatives of cyanide where both the R-CN and R-NC isomeric compounds can be prepared. Experimental findings sporadically indicate that there are complexes where cyanide is bonded via the nitrogen end. Such species are formed when an inert cobalt(III) cyano-complex oxidises the labile chromium(II) aqua ion²:

The isocyanochromium(III) complex then isomerises to the carbon bonded species:

Unfortunately there is no information on the relative stability of the two species. The kinetic studies³ provided only a limiting value for the quotient:

$$Q = \frac{[\text{CrCN}^{2+}]}{[\text{CrNC}^{2+}]} \geq 20.$$

An N bonded cyanocomplex is also formed transiently in the following redox reaction⁴:

Raman spectroscopic evidence was recently found⁵ that in liquid ammonia solution the following equilibrium should be taken into account:

(y is unknown).

All these species exist in solution. The preparation of two isomeric isocyanocomplexes (cis $[\text{Co}(\text{NC})_2 \text{trien}] \text{ClO}_4$) has been briefly described⁶:

Unfortunately, we could not obtain the compounds and the existence of the above complexes seems to be doubtful.

It seems likely, however, that a certain fraction of the coordinated cyano groups is bonded via the nitrogen atom, and the ratio of the number of the nitrogen bonded to carbon bonded ligands depends on the central ion and the other ligands in the coordination sphere.

Cyanide as a bridging ligand: Cyanide is ideally suited to act as a bridging ligand and in fact there is an enormous number of polynuclear complexes involving cyanide bridges. There are three possibilities for the bonding:

- i) Linear or nearly linear bonding: M-CN-M'
- ii) Bent bonding involving carbon atom only

- iii) Carbon (or nitrogen) atom is bonded to one metal center, while the π system makes a bond to the second metal.

The M-CN-M' is the most frequent arrangement. This occurs in the giant molecules of the prussian blue and its analogues. Recently two isomeric μ -cyano-complex was prepared^{7,8} and the structural data determined^{9,10}. Pentacyanocobalt(III)- μ -cyano-pentaamminecobalt(III) was obtained by the thermal dehydration:

while the isomeric μ -isocyanocomplex was prepared by the reaction:

According to the X-ray studies there is a small but distinct difference in the structure of the isomers and in both cases there is a considerable deviation from the linearity in the bonding Co-CN-Co.

The only example¹¹ for the bent bridge structure is $[\text{Cu}(\text{CN})\text{NH}_3]_n$. There is no definite evidence for bridging via the π system, but the type of heteropolynuclear complexes¹² involving $\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_2$ and a coordinatively saturated transition metal complex having at least two cyano groups in cis position, seems suspicious and worthy for a structural study.

Formation of mixed ligand complexes: The conspicuous tendency for the formation of mixed ligand complexes involving one or more cyano groups is due to the peculiar bonding properties of cyanide.

As a pseudohalide ion it has a great tendency to form mixed ligand complexes with halide ions. As a characteristic π -bonding ligand, it favours to form mixed ligand complexes with other π -bonding ligands. A particular class of mixed ligand complexes is in which the simultaneous coordination of the different isoelectronic ligands CN^- , CO , NO^+ , N_2 and C_2^{2-} should be considered. The cyano-carbonyl and the cyano-nitrosyl complexes are well known. There is evidence for the formation of cyano-dinitrogen complexes in the following reaction¹³:

The investigation of the complexes containing acetylide and cyanide ions seems to be a very promising field. It is likely that such a complex is formed as an intermediate in the CuCl catalysed reaction between HCN and acetylene.

Stability of cyanocomplexes. Although there are many controversial thermodynamic stability constants referring to different cyanocomplexes¹⁴, it is beyond doubt that the most stable complexes in solution are found among them. In many cases, the ratio of successive formation constants (K_i/K_{i+1}) is much less than the statistical one due to the back-donation. It follows then, that in such cases only cumulative stability constants can be obtained. In spite of the great efforts only the brutto stability constant is available for $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, $\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$. In these cases only the following inequalities can be stated:

$$K_i < \sqrt[i]{\beta_N} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1)$$

$$K_N > \sqrt[N]{\beta_N}$$

In comparing the stability constants one always should bear in mind that the number of bonds involved in the reaction must be considered. The free energy calculated from the stability constant is the difference between the free energy of the corresponding solvocomplex and that of the complex in question.

In case of $\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ the exact value even of β_4 is not known, but a reasonable lower limit has been determined¹⁵: $\lg \beta_4 > 6.5$. Based on the former inequalities, it means that $\lg K_4$ is probably bigger than 20. In case of the $\text{Hg}^{2+}-\text{CN}^-$ system the stepwise stability constants could be determined¹⁶ and $\lg K_1$ is 18.0 at 2 °C. These data and considerations indicate that some of the metal-cyanide bonds belong to the most stable chemical bonds.

Redox behaviour of cyanide. Cyanide can be easily oxidized to cyanogen, the standard redox potential of the following reaction

is + 0.37 V. Cyanogen is usually prepared by adding cyanide to a hot concentrated solution of copper(II) sulphate. However, when copper(II) is added to a cooled concentrated solution of cyanide the redox reactions also take place, but cyanogen is captured in the coordination sphere of the copper(I) formed¹⁷ :

There are two possibilities for the complex formation of cyanogen. First, that cyanogen itself acts as a ligand ; secondly, that analogously to the halide-halogen systems, a tricyanide ion is formed and is coordinated :

There are evidence that cyanogen itself is coordinated and acts as a bridging ligand in complexes formed in the following reactions^{18,19} :

In many cases, cyanogen reacts with complexes of metal centre of low oxidation state by oxidative addition. The first step is most likely the formation of a cyanogen complex, which is followed by the electron transfer reaction and the formation of the corresponding dicyano complex.

The assumed interaction between cyanide and cyanogen has been studied by us. Because of the experimental difficulties no exact value of the stability constant could be determined, but spectrophotometric and extraction experiments²⁰ unambiguously indicate the existence of the species $(\text{CN})_3^-$. The approximate value of the stability constant (25 °C aqueous solution, ionic strength 1) is about 2.

Complex formation may even stabilize this ion, but at present no evidence is available on the coordination of $(\text{CN})_3^-$.

Biological and prebiological importance of cyanide. The poisonous effect of cyanide ion is well known and it is mainly due to the reaction of cyanide with haem in and different metalloenzymes. On the other hand, cyanide is a constituent of the vitally important vitamin B₁₂. In plants cyanide containing glycosides e.g. amygdalines frequently occur.

The prebiotic importance of cyanide is well documented and in fact there were speculations about the role of cyano compounds in the origin of life as early as the turn of century. The possible role of HCN

and $(\text{CN})_2$ in the prebiotic formation of nucleobases, amino acids and even proteins is treated in many papers and the reader can find data for the original papers in any book on chemical evolution. In this paper, I would like to stress only that cyano complexes of transition metals certainly played an important, perhaps a crucial role in the chemical evolution. It is beyond doubt that no living system exists without transition metal ions. Therefore, one must assume, that there was a certain stage in the chemical evolution when the availability of some metal complexes was a prerequisite for the further development towards the living state. In the primordial period CN^- —and interestingly enough each of the isoelectronic species—was one of the most common species. Considering the extremely big stability of the cyanocomplexes of transition metal ions one can conclude that the prebiotic soup contained cyanocomplexes. This assumption is supported by model experiments in which old rocks were extracted by dilute aqueous cyanide solution²¹.

Exploratory experiments indicated that certain reactions of transition metal cyanocomplexes leads to the formation of nucleobases, amino acids ; some compounds have catalytic properties in redox reactions, these species may be regarded as archetypes of metalloenzymes²². It seems therefore that prebiotic coordination chemistry overlaps in a great extent with the chemistry of cyanocomplexes. This new approach of the problem of the origin of life probably will give a new impact to this intriguing field.

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